

Observed Spatiotemporal Variability in the Annual Sea Level Cycle Along the Global Coast

Key Points:

- The annual sea level cycle varied in amplitude and phase since the mid-20th century at many tide gauge locations
- There are well-defined regional clusters of tide gauges where the annual sea level cycle exhibits coherent variability
- Changes in the annual sea level cycle are linked to dominant modes of climate variability such as: AMO/NAO (Baltic), and ENSO/PDO (Pacific)

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Abstract Changes in the seasonal sea level cycle can modulate the flooding risk along coastlines. Here, we use harmonic analysis to quantify changes in the amplitude and phase of the annual component of the sea level cycle at 798 tide gauge locations along the global coastline where long records are available. We identify coastal hotspots by applying clustering methods revealing coherent regions with similar patterns of variability in the annual sea level cycle. Results show that for most tide gauges the annual amplitude reached its maximum after 1970 and its peak typically occurs during the fall season of the respective hemisphere. Many tide gauges exhibit non-stationarity in the annual cycle in terms of amplitude and/or phase. For example, at 226 tide gauges we find significant trends in the amplitude (either increasing or decreasing) for the time period after 1970; while several sites (50 in total), mostly in the Mediterranean and around Pacific islands, experienced phase changes leading to shifts in the timing of the peak of the annual cycle by more than a month over their entire record. Our results highlight the importance of accounting for potential non-stationarity in seasonal mean sea level cycles along coastlines.

Plain Language Summary The seasonal sea level cycle is the pattern of high and low mean sea level (MSL) observed throughout the year at a location. Shifts in the timing of the maximum sea level impact coastlines with increased risk of flooding if the higher MSL occurs at a time of year when factors like storms or high tides are also at their peak. The seasonal cycle consists of semi-annual and annual components; here we focus on the dominating annual sea level cycle (ASLC) after decomposing the MSL at 798 locations into amplitude and phase components which describe the variability and timing of the MSL yearly peak, respectively. We find that MSL amplitude typically reaches its maximum during the fall in each hemisphere. Coastal hotspots in the North Atlantic have been identified with coherent regions showing similar patterns in their ASLC variability. We find 226 locations with significant trends in amplitude and 50 locations where the yearly MSL peak has changed by more than a month throughout the record. Additionally, we find relationships between the MSL annual amplitudes and climate indices characterizing regional-scale climate phenomena. Our results provide a comprehensive description of changes in the ASLC along portions of the global coastline.

1. Introduction

Many coastal locations worldwide have experienced the impacts of sea level change. This includes saltwater intrusion, freshwater resource contamination, ecosystem disruptions, surge propagation, coastal infrastructure damage, and other socio-economic impacts related to flooding, which are especially observable in low-lying areas (IPCC, 2023; Smith et al., 2010). In addition to projections of sea level changes, it is important to understand modulations of regular and predictable cycles of mean sea level (MSL). These can coincide with other natural climate processes or with components of extreme sea level, such as storm surge, to heighten the resulting total sea level at a particular location (Wahl et al., 2014). For example, when the maximum MSL for a given year aligns with a region's seasonal maximum of storm activity or with the seasonal high tides (often colloquially referred to as king tides), the likelihood for flooding is relatively higher as opposed to when the MSL peaks occur out of phase.

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The seasonal sea level cycle (SSLC) describes the sea level pattern observed annually due to the regional climate characteristics of a location. The SSLC as measured by coastal tide gauges is the result of different mechanisms with varying importance depending on the location: wind stress, atmospheric pressure, seasonal ice melt, steric sea level variations associated with heat fluxes and water exchange with the atmosphere, ocean circulation, precipitation, and river discharge (e.g., Qu et al., 2022). In this analysis it is represented by the sum of annual and semi-annual harmonics with amplitudes and phases that correspond to the magnitude and timing of monthly MSL maxima and minima. Changes in the amplitude over time lead to larger differences between the troughs and peaks, while shifts in the phase can move the peak closer to or away from the storm surge season. The SSLC is often assumed to be stationary in time and is removed in studies considering sea level variability, but non-stationarity of the SSLC has been found to play a significant role in contributing to coastal sea level variations (Feng et al., 2015). The SSLC has been studied previously at the global scale (e.g., Gill & Niller, 1973; Pattullo et al., 1955; Pugh & Woodworth, 2014; Vinogradov et al., 2008) and across specific regions worldwide (e.g., Amiruddin et al., 2015; Barbosa et al., 2007; Barbosa & Silva, 2009; Calafat et al., 2018; Dangendorf et al., 2012, 2013; Feng et al., 2015; Hünicke & Zorita, 2008; Marcos & Tsimplis, 2007; Plag & Tsimplis, 1999; Torres & Tsimplis, 2012; Wahl et al., 2014).

However, these studies either focused on the mean SSLC or assessed changes in individual regions; changes of the SSLC over time in terms of amplitude and phase have not been comprehensively assessed on a global scale. Here, our central aim is to analyze how the annual component of the SSLC, hereafter referred to as the annual sea level cycle (ASLC), observed by tide gauges globally has varied in space and time. We extend previous analyses (e.g., Calafat et al., 2018; Wahl et al., 2014) to a broader scope of the global coastline and add investigations of the annual phase component. We assess how much the amplitude and phase of the annual cycle has fluctuated around the mean in the past and identify recent trends. In this context, we also identify clusters of coherent variability in the annual amplitude for the North Atlantic coastlines, as an example, where we have a dense network of tide gauges. Finally, we compare relevant climate indices to the annual amplitudes to detect whether any significant relationships exist. By doing this, we provide a comprehensive description of spatiotemporal variability in the ASLC along gauged portions of the global coastline.

2. Data

Monthly MSL data measured by tide gauges was obtained from the Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level (PSMSL) database (Holgate et al., 2013; Woodworth & Player, 2003). The tide gauge data used are a combination of the revised local reference (RLR) subset and the metric data subset. A total of 856 tide gauges located across the globe were chosen according to a minimum record length of 30 years. Since the focus of this study is on changes in the ASLC along the global coasts, 58 tide gauges were discarded based on locations in lakes, rivers, or near glaciers where the seasonal cycles of water levels are heavily influenced by different processes than the coastal ASLC (Amiruddin et al., 2015; Tsimplis & Woodworth, 1994) and hence outside the scope of this study; we also compared different approaches for the harmonic fit (see Methods for details) and the comparison helped identifying few tide gauges where suspicious data affected the results. This resulted in the final set of 798 tide gauges that are used to analyze the ASLC and its changes over time (see Figure 1 for the locations and record lengths). Additionally, climate indices were downloaded from the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration's Physical Sciences Laboratory (NOAA PSL). The indices used are: El Niño-Southern Oscillation 3 (ENSO), North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO), Atlantic Multidecadal Oscillation (AMO), and the Pacific Decadal Oscillation (PDO) because of their large-scale influence on climate.

3. Methods

3.1. Harmonic Analysis

Following Wahl et al. (2014), we perform a harmonic analysis to deconstruct the MSL into the components of interest. We fit a regression model to moving 5-year windows with no more than 2 years of missing data (also see Section 3.2) of the monthly MSL time series and shift the window by 1 month each time step, as has been done in previous studies (Amiruddin et al., 2015; Plag & Tsimplis, 1999; Tsimplis & Woodworth, 1994):

$$\text{MSL}(t) = \text{MSL}_0 + at + A_1 \cos[2\pi(t - p_1)] + A_2 \cos\left[\frac{2\pi}{0.5}(t - p_2)\right] \quad (1)$$

Figure 1. (a) Number of years of monthly MSL data available from 798 tide gauges. Records longer than 100 years (90 tide gauges) are all shown in yellow. (b) Last year of tide gauge record used where 112 tide gauges ending before the year 1990 are shown in purple.

Equation 1 shows how the time changing $MSL(t)$ is decomposed into four terms with a total of six parameters: the MSL_0 (constant mean value) for the respective time window (where t is the time in years), a linear trend a , the annual and semi-annual amplitudes, A_1 and A_2 , and the annual and semi-annual phase, p_1 and p_2 . The harmonic constituents are estimated over the 5-year window and assigned to the center (i.e., 15th day of the 30th month for each time window). Therefore, there are no values during the first and last 30 months. The phases are extracted from the model and calculated based on simple trigonometry (Equation 2) in reference to a fixed time frame, so that the degrees can be interpreted as months of the year. January is the starting point at 0° . Each calendar month of the year increases by approximately 30° for the annual phase, reaching a total of 360° by the end of December. Since the MSL data we use from PSMSL is monthly, leap years are accounted for as an average MSL value of all days in that month. To interpret the phase estimate of degrees as a day in a leap year, we then calculate Equation 2 using a total of 366 days in a year.

$$\text{Annual phase degree: } p_1 = \frac{(360^\circ)(\text{nth day})}{\text{Total days of year}} \quad (2)$$

3.2. Sensitivity Analysis

To assure robustness of our results, we perform different sensitivity tests. We compare Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) estimation to robust fit for deriving regression coefficients and we contrast the results against the Bayesian approach by Calafat et al. (2018) at select sites. We also apply jackknife resampling of the 5-year moving windows to assess how missing data (e.g., individual extreme years) can influence the results. Lastly, we test the precision of the phase estimates since our model returns phase degree values of daily resolution from monthly data.

3.2.1. Models: Ordinary Least Squares Estimation Versus Robust Fit

We compare OLS and robust fit to estimate regression parameters and found that the models produce different results in some locations. It is known that OLS results can be influenced by outliers. Hence, to reduce the effect of outliers on the results, we run the model using the robust fit Huber estimation (Huber, 1981). We compare results from both model estimation methods and chose to move forward with the robust fit model which was found to be overall more reliable than OLS. In most places results are similar, but to identify tide gauges where data inconsistencies could lead to larger differences and influence our results, we visually inspect the data from tide gauges which exhibit a large RMSE difference between the 2 models and the annual amplitude estimates. For some tide gauges, we find vertical shifts due to earthquakes, for example, in locations around Japan. We identify the change points and remove the years before or after datum shifts; if less than 30 years of consistent data are left, the tide gauges are discarded. After carefully assessing the data quality those tide gauges are retained. This process leads to the final set of 798 tide gauges, for which we use the results from the robust fit approach for further analysis.

Calafat et al. (2018) studied the SSLC in the United States (U.S.) Gulf and Atlantic coasts proposing a Bayesian method as an alternative to a harmonic analysis. Under certain conditions, the Bayesian method is more robust in capturing fluctuations, but it is also much more computationally demanding, especially for our global tide gauge analysis. After testing it for several stations, we find that the differences in the results are small (not shown) and do not affect our overall conclusions and hence we proceed with the simpler regression method.

3.2.2. Jackknife Resampling

The next sensitivity test we apply is jackknife resampling on the 5-year moving windows. For each 5-year window we remove data from 1 year and fit the model, then remove the next year's data and fit the model, and so on, until all 5 years in the window were discarded. This gives for each time step five different estimates of the amplitudes and phases. At each tide gauge, we quantify the spread of the resampling results by calculating the range and circular standard deviation (see Section 3.4 Equation 3 for more explanation on circular statistics) between the five different estimates of the model's amplitude and phase components, respectively. From this, we obtain a resampling-range (or circular standard deviation) value for each time step (i.e., every month). Next, we find the median resampling-range (or circular standard deviation) value for each tide gauge over time. For the annual amplitude component, we find that the median range of resampling results varies from 0.8 to 8.3 cm across tide gauge locations, with a median value of 1.8 cm and a standard deviation of 0.9 cm. For the annual phase component, we find that the median circular standard deviation of resampling results from all tide gauges varies from 2.7 to 36.4° with a median of 11.9°. From these results and previous literature (Amiruddin et al., 2015; Plag & Tsimplis, 1999; Tsimplis & Woodworth, 1994), we confirm that choosing a 5-year time window for the harmonic analysis is a reasonable choice.

3.2.3. Phase Precision Testing

We produce 700 synthetic 5-year-long time series (to hypothetically represent 700 different tide gauge locations) of daily values of an annual sinusoid with known randomized phase. Then, we compute monthly averages from the daily values. We apply the harmonic analysis to these monthly time series to determine a phase estimate. To compute the error in estimation we take the difference between the estimated phase and the true phase that was initially input to create the synthetic data. From the distribution of 700 time series we incur an error in the phase estimates between 0 and 1.2° different than the true phases. This shows that our model reliably estimates the phases at daily resolution despite the monthly resolution of the input data.

3.3. Quantifying Changes in Amplitude

From the moving harmonic analysis, we obtain time series of the MSL annual and semi-annual amplitudes. In this study we focus solely on changes in the annual amplitude because it is the dominant factor in most locations, apart from the tropics and a few sites in Antarctica where there are relatively fewer tide gauges (Vinogradov et al., 2008). Previous regional studies of the SSLC (e.g., Calafat et al., 2018; Wahl et al., 2014) also emphasized the annual component rather than the semi-annual, and in line with those studies the following discussions of amplitude and phase all refer to the annual component. In a first assessment, we derive the value of the maximum amplitude at all tide gauge locations and identify in which year it occurred. We do this for two time periods: the

entire record of the respective tide gauge (for all 798 tide gauges), and the period post-1970 (for 623 tide gauges with data after 1970). We further quantify the relative variability in annual amplitude by deriving the standard deviation and the ratio between the mean amplitude and the maximum amplitude.

To assess long-term changes, we fit a linear trend to the annual amplitude time series of the subset focusing on the post-1970 period to derive comparable results across sites. The significance of the trends is assessed using the two-sigma standard error estimated by the Newey-West method which accounts for autocorrelation and heteroskedasticity in the time series (Newey & West, 1987).

Finally, following Calafat et al. (2018), we also assess changes in the number of 95th percentile threshold exceedances of the amplitude during different decades. In combination with the linear trend analysis and the assessment of when the maximum amplitude occurred, this provides additional insights about amplitude changes. We compare the difference between the number of 95th percentile threshold exceedances that occur in the last decade of the record to the number of exceedances in the first decade post-1970 at tide gauges with at least 20 years of data after 1970, no more than 10 years of continuous data gaps over that time period, and overall no gaps greater than 25% of the record data length (623 tide gauges).

3.4. Changes in Phase

To identify changes in the phase we use circular statistics (Berens, 2009). This method has been used in previous studies to measure the seasonality of flooding (Veatch & Villarini, 2020; Villarini, 2016) and across other scientific fields that apply periodic data such as phases of the moon, wind direction, animal migration paths, neuroscience, criminology, and more (Bowers et al., 2000; Gao et al., 2006; Cochran et al., 2004, etc.). There are other methods addressing timing and phase that are used more extensively by the tidal community and consider the sun's mean ecliptic longitude, but it sacrifices the convenient use of calendar days (Ray et al., 2021). In our study, the phase describes when during the year MSL reaches its maximum. Quantifying phase values over different 5-year windows allows us to evaluate whether the peaks of the ASLC for a location have shifted over time. Circular statistics allow the phase to vary continuously across 0 (360) degrees into the next year. For example, in some locations, the ASLC generally peaks between August to September (phase of 210–270°), whereas in others the range spans across calendar years, for instance, November to January (300–30°).

Considering the angular nature of the phase time series derived from the harmonic analysis, to accurately reflect instances where the range may cross over 0°, we compute the circular standard deviation defined as:

$$s = \sqrt{-2 \ln R} \quad (3)$$

where R is the mean resultant vector length (Berens, 2009). R gives a value from 0 to 1 describing a uniform dispersion (0) throughout the polar circle plane, or concentration in one direction (1). In this application, a phase concentrated in one direction (with an R value near 1) implies a stronger seasonality, meaning the seasonal pattern is more evident of distinct monthly fluctuations, instead of dispersed throughout the months of the year.

3.5. Regional Coherence and Links to Climate Modes

To identify spatial coherence across locations, we apply a clustering algorithm to group tide gauges according to their patterns of ASLC amplitude changes (Li et al., 2021). We use the k -means Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) approach via Python's "tslearn" package (Tavenard et al., 2020). K -means partitions the data into k number of clusters, or groups, based on their similarity (MacQueen, 1967). The similarity is commonly measured by the squared Euclidean distance of the data points, but in this study, we instead use a modification of k -means where we apply DTW as the similarity measure because it detects similar patterns in the time series regardless of whether those features are contemporaneous (Aghabozorgi et al., 2015). DTW warps the path between time series by choosing the closest points between the time series based on the Levenshtein distance calculation (Petitjean et al., 2011). Cluster centroids are computed for each resulting group of time series, where the centroid represents an average sequence that is followed by the rest of the time series within the respective cluster via DTW barycenter averaging (DBA). The amplitude time series are scaled to have zero mean and unit variance to disregard the magnitude of the changes, since our goal is to identify regions where relatively high or low values occur (near-)

simultaneously. This approach captures flexible similarities and focuses on similar trajectories between the time series, allowing us to cluster according to the shape of the time series rather than the range of the data.

We focus on clustering tide gauges within the North Atlantic basin because of its dense network of tide gauges with long overlapping periods, and thus, we satisfy the requirement of the algorithm to use a consistent time frame across tide gauges. For this analysis, we select the period from 1980 to 2015 as tradeoff to retain a relatively large number of tide gauges with overlapping records while also having reasonable coverage of the entire North Atlantic coast. Initially clustering tide gauges across the entire North Atlantic basin resulted in the algorithm to group together tide gauges in a scattered manner without obvious physical reasons. Therefore, we decided to split the North Atlantic further into eastern and western parts to ensure more coherent and reasonable clusters. To determine the optimal number of clusters we use the elbow curve method as guidance (Camus et al., 2011), where we compute the standard deviation across time series in a cluster as a function of varying numbers of clusters, and we check the tipping point of the curve.

For each cluster we compute the percent variance explained (PVE) by the mean time series of the cluster (Rashid et al., 2019). This shows how much of the variability in amplitude is explained by the cluster mean. Here we take the variance of the amplitude time series for each tide gauge in a cluster (scaled with unit variance = 1), subtract the cluster mean from each individual time series, and compute the variance again. The difference between the initial variance and the resulting variance after removing the cluster mean reveals what portion of the variability in amplitude was contributed by the cluster mean. We multiply this value by 100 to obtain the PVE.

Lastly, we analyze the MSL annual amplitudes from individual tide gauges in relation to the 5 strongest (positive and negative) years of relevant climate indices. To account for data gaps, we first drop the years where there are less than 10 months of MSL data available. Next, we require at least a 30-year length of overlapping data between the tide gauges and the respective climate index. We compute an annual average of the climate indices and identify the 5 strongest years of both the positive and negative phases of each climate index. For those years, we apply the 5-year harmonic analysis on the MSL data, compute the differences between the annual amplitudes estimated during the years where climate indices were strongly positive versus the years where the climate indices were strongly negative, and normalize those differences by the mean amplitude of the respective tide gauge for comparison. We assess whether the ASLC amplitude is significantly different (using standard errors estimated by our harmonic regression model (Ku, 1966)) during the positive and negative phases to quantify the impact of the climate indices.

4. Results

4.1. Changes in Amplitude

In agreement with Pugh and Woodworth (2014), the highest mean annual amplitudes, exceeding 20 cm, are found mainly in East Asia and northern Australia (Figure 2a). Small mean amplitude values below 6 cm are distributed throughout the globe including along the east coast of Canada, the west coast of South America, Pacific Islands, and South Africa (Figure 2a). About 95% of the 798 tide gauges analyzed have a mean amplitude below 17 cm, and only 1% above 20 cm. However, approximately 10% reach a maximum amplitude above 20 cm at some point throughout their record, when accounting for non-stationarity. As shown in Figure 2b, these larger maximum amplitudes are located across the Northern Hemisphere and a few in northern Australia.

We find that over 70% of the 798 tide gauges' annual amplitudes peak after 1970. When considering only the post-1970 period, over half of the 623 tide gauges with records past that time frame peak after 1990 (Figure 3), and over half in the North American region peak during the most recent decade (after 2010). In northern Europe there is a concentration of peak amplitudes that occur before 1990, while the earliest peaks (1970s) occur in the northern Russian coast and at several other locations around the globe.

We consider a subset of 623 tide gauges for the trend analysis (Figure 4a). The subset is composed of tide gauge records that fulfill the following criteria: they cover the period 1970 onwards with more than 20 years of data, have no more than 10 years of continuous data gaps, and no gaps larger than 25% of the data length. Significant trends in annual amplitude at the 95% confidence level (according to the Newey-West estimator; see Section 3.3) occur at a total of 226 locations. Out of those, 122 are positive and located along the U.S. East Coast, Mediterranean, Australia, western South America, U.S. southwest coast, and parts of southeast Asia; 104 tide gauges experience negative trends and are mostly located around the Baltic Sea, U.S. northwest coast, Bay of Bengal and

Figure 2. Global maps of annual MSL amplitudes for 798 tide gauges. (a) Mean annual amplitude of MSL (cm). The colorbar is cut off at 18 cm where 33 tide gauges above 18 cm are shown in yellow. (b) Maximum annual amplitude of MSL (cm) of the entire record where 139 tide gauges with values above 18 cm are shown in yellow. (c) The standard deviation of the annual amplitude. The color bar is cut off at a standard deviation of 3 cm where 74 tide gauges with a standard deviation above 3 cm are shown in yellow. (d) The ratio of the mean annual amplitude to the maximum annual amplitude for each respective tide gauge.

Andaman Sea. Over 75% of the tide gauges with significant trends show amplitude changes at a rate greater than ± 0.5 mm/year, and 80 tide gauges greater than ± 1 mm/year (Figure 4a).

At 104 tide gauges, we find that the 95th percentile of the amplitude is exceeded more often during the most recent decade of the records than during the first decade post-1970 (Figure 4b). In 78 locations, there are more exceedances during the first decade post-1970, and there is no change of exceedances in 44 tide gauges. Taking Key West as an example, over its entire record, there are 61 out of 1225 months when the annual amplitude exceeds its 95th percentile of about 10 cm; these exceedances all occurred after the year 2000, and 45 of those between 2007 and 2011. Neighboring tide gauge stations throughout Florida, Georgia, and the Carolinas also exhibit annual amplitudes exceeding their 95th percentiles during the last decade, but none at the beginning of their records.

Globally (across all regions where tide gauge data are available), the largest differences between the number of exceedances are found along most of the Gulf of Mexico, East coast of the U.S., and the northern coast of Australia with most of the monthly exceedances of the 95th percentile occurring during the most recent decade than during the 1970s, confirming the trend results. In contrast, the Baltic experienced higher amplitudes during the 1970s (especially in Kalix and Forsmark in Sweden) than during the most recent decade in most of their tide gauges. This corresponds again with the negative amplitude trends observed in the Baltic in Figure 4a, but the results are less pronounced, indicating that changes are non-linear. Strong values in both the trend (Figure 4a) and the positive difference of 95th percentile exceedances (Figure 4b) indicate a continuous trend post-1970, whereas a small trend with a large difference of exceedances between the first and last decades indicates a relatively flat curve (i.e., small trend) with a recent sharp change (i.e., large difference in 95th percentile exceedances). On the other hand, a strong trend with small difference in exceedances, could indicate an overall change throughout much of the record but a recent change in the opposite direction. This is the case in the Baltic, for example, where we find strong negative trends but relatively small differences in the 95th percentile exceedances.

Figure 3. Year when the annual amplitude of MSL peaks for the period post-1970 for 623 tide gauges.

Figure 4. (a) Trends in annual amplitude (mm/year) shown for tide gauges with records at least 20 years long for the period after 1970. Results are shown for 226 tide gauges where trends are significant according to the Newey-West estimator. For illustration purposes the color bar is cut off at 2 mm (16 tide gauges have trends with a magnitude over 2 mm). (b) Normalized difference in the number of times (months) that the annual amplitude exceeds its 95th percentile between two time periods: the last decade of the tide gauge record and the first decade of data post-1970. If the difference is positive, it indicates that the annual amplitude exceeded its 95th percentile more often during the last decade of the record than during the first decade post-1970.

4.2. Changes in Phase

Globally, the mean annual phases for most tide gauge locations (510 out of 798) indicate an ASLC peak during the fall season of the respective hemisphere, following the time integral of solar heating (September to November for the Northern Hemisphere; March to May for the Southern Hemisphere) (Figure 5a). For the rest of the sites, it peaks during summer in 192 tide gauges, 83 in winter, and 13 in spring. In addition to the mean of the phase, we also assess its variability (Figure 5b) to quantify how dispersed the peaks are during the year.

Recalling that 30° represent approximately 1 month, regions such as the Mediterranean, Baltic Sea, and the northeast coast of North America are some hotspots where the phase vary most over time ($>30^\circ$). For example, Brest (France) has a circular standard deviation value of 19° , and in the Baltic Sea the tide gauge of Swinoujscie (Poland) has a circular standard deviation of 33° . In contrast, the region around Japan exhibits small values between 0 and 5° , indicating that the peak of the annual cycle always occurs around the same time.

In Key West (Florida), the circular standard deviation is also small (8°). At this location, the ASLC peaks between September and October (Figure 6a), and the greater amplitude values (above 10 cm) start to occur after 1993 (Figure 6b). Similarly, in St. Petersburg (western Florida), the phase indicates that the ASLC peaks have shifted from the month of August to September in recent years. Similar results for St. Petersburg were reported in Wahl et al. (2014). Brest (France), on the other hand, typically peaks between October and December, although in recent years, some peaks occurred in January. At the tide gauge of Swinoujscie (Poland), the annual cycle peaks

Figure 5. (a) Global map of circular mean annual phase (degrees) where each calendar month is represented by 30-degree increments (b) Circular standard deviation of phase (degrees). The color bar is cut off at 30° where 50 tide gauges with a circular standard deviation above 30° (approximately 1 month) are shown in yellow.

mostly between July to October, but with high variability including peaks across all months of the year (Figure 6f).

4.3. Regional Coherence of Amplitude Changes

The geographic clustering of the time-variable ASLC amplitudes is performed separately for the northwestern and northeastern Atlantic basins, following similar regionalization boundaries as in Enriquez et al. (2020). For this analysis, we use tide gauge records covering the period from 1980 to 2015, resulting in 41 tide gauges in the northwestern and 80 tide gauges in the northeastern Atlantic regions, respectively. As mentioned in Methods, the analysis is restricted to this time period in order to retain the maximum amount of tide gauges with overlapping records and data completeness, while achieving reasonable coverage of the coastline. Note that we include the Mediterranean Sea, but we omit tide gauges located in the Black Sea. After testing several numbers of clusters suggested by the elbow curve (see Methods), we chose to use 3 clusters for the northwestern (Figure 7) and 4 clusters for the northeastern Atlantic regions (Figure 8). A total of 6 tide gauges were discarded as they did not fit

Figure 6. (a) De-trended monthly MSL plotted for each month of the year (gray) for the length of the respective tide gauge record. The black line represents the long-term mean and the blue line represents the median. (b) The month in which the annual phase (degrees) occurs over time. Color bar represents the time of the record in years. The radius of each circle on the polar plot represents the annual amplitude (cm). Months in red font represent the summer season and blue font represents the winter season of the respective hemisphere.

well within their assigned clusters. Those are mostly located in complex regions such the Strait of Gibraltar or in very high latitudes; two from the western Gulf of Mexico were assigned to the East coast (Cluster 1) but did not match well with the rest and hence were discarded from the cluster analysis.

Figure 7. Clustering (*k*-means DTW) annual amplitude time series from the period of 1980–2015. (a) Map of 41 tide gauges in the Northwest Atlantic region and the clusters they were assigned. (b) Annual amplitude time series of the individual records within clusters (gray) and the mean cluster time series (colored). Number of members in each cluster: Cluster 1 (21 members), Cluster 2 (8 members), Cluster 3 (12 members).

Tide gauges in the northwestern Atlantic region show spatial coherence in the ASLC amplitude time series, especially in the southeastern U.S. and Gulf of Mexico coastlines (Cluster 3 in Figure 7). Similarly, tide gauges north of Cape Hatteras are distinguished as a separate cluster (Cluster 1). Both clusters exhibit an upwards tendency, particularly after 1996. Meanwhile, the amplitude time series of the northernmost tide gauges in Canada (Cluster 2) are less resemblant to their cluster mean (blue time series in Figure 7b). This region consists of complex bay systems and bathymetry which may lead to local effects overshadowing any regional coherent changes in the ASLC.

In the northeastern Atlantic region (Figure 8), Cluster 1 (blue) coherently groups all tide gauges in the Baltic along with some in the North Sea. Cluster 2 (yellow) assimilates the ASLC patterns of tide gauges in the Mediterranean with those along the Bay of Biscay and the English Channel. Tide gauges on the Norwegian coast are split between Cluster 3 (red) and Cluster 4 (green), while Cluster 3 also includes tide gauges on the east coast of the United Kingdom (UK) and Netherlands.

The percent variance explained (PVE) by each cluster's mean time series (Figure 9) shows how well the cluster mean describes the overall amplitude pattern of the individual tide gauges pertaining to the cluster. Low, near-zero percentages indicate that for certain outlier tide gauges, the mean time series of the cluster (colored time series in Figures 7 and 8) does not explain the amplitude variability at those locations. In the Northwest Atlantic the median PVE of Cluster 1 (north of Cape Hatteras) is the highest (87%), as the mean cluster time series explains 40%–95% of

Figure 8. Clustering (*k*-means DTW) annual amplitude time series from the period of 1980–2015. (a) Map of 80 tide gauges in the Northeast Atlantic region (Europe) and the clusters they were assigned. (b) Annual amplitude time series of the individual records within clusters (gray) and the mean cluster time series (colored). Number of tide gauge members in each cluster: Cluster 1 (42 members), Cluster 2 (18 members), Cluster 3 (13 members), Cluster 4 (7 members).

Figure 9. Boxplots of the percent variance explained (PVE) by the mean time series of each cluster. The colors of the boxes match the cluster to which it pertains on the maps in Figures 7a and 8a; the horizontal red lines are the medians, the red crosses (+) are outliers, and the bottom and top edges of each box represent the 25th and 75th percentiles.

the variance of the individual time series in the cluster. Cluster 2 has the lowest median value (49%) and only explains between 20% and 60% of the variability of the individual time series. In the Northeast Atlantic, the mean time series of Cluster 1 explains about 93% of the variance for those tide gauges in the Baltic. This indicates that the variability of all the time series within that cluster is well explained by the mean cluster time series. Cluster 4 has a small spread (likely due to the small number of tide gauges in this cluster).

In order to link the ASLC amplitude variability to large scale climate variations, we compare ASLC amplitudes during the five strongest years of each climate index's positive and negative phases (Figure 10). During ENSO, significant differences in amplitude are found in 233 tide gauges out of the 764 tide gauges whose record overlaps at least 30 years. The NAO, AMO, and PDO show significant differences at 181 out of 710, 276 out of 712, and 250 out of 712 tide gauges, respectively. In the northeastern Pacific there is a coherent stretch of higher ASLC amplitudes on the western U.S. coast during positive ENSO, while on the eastern U.S. coast smaller amplitudes occur during positive ENSO. During positive NAO, higher amplitudes occur in the Baltic while they are low when AMO is positive. Both the AMO and NAO show a distinct change from the southwestern U.S. coast to the northwestern U.S. coast between their positive/negative phases. Amplitudes in northern Australia and the majority of Japan are smaller during positive AMO and PDO.

5. Discussion

Previous literature has documented the amplitude of the seasonal cycle in MSL for different parts of the world. This analysis goes further (focusing on the ASLC) to investigate those changes over time for the entire global coast where tide gauge data is available. From assessing the mean SSLC globally, Pugh and Woodworth (2014) display comparable amplitude and phase outputs resulting from a harmonic analysis of tide gauges in the same dataset

Figure 10. Differences in ASLC amplitude (normalized by their mean amplitude) between the 5 years with the strongest positive and negative phases of the climate indices. Red colors indicate that ASLC amplitudes are larger when the respective climate mode is positive. Results are shown for tide gauges where MSL and climate index data overlap for at least 30 years and where ASLC amplitude differences for positive versus negative climate mode phases are significant at the 95% confidence level. For illustration purposes, the color bar cuts off 37 tide gauges with normalized differences greater than 1 unit.

(PSMSL) that we use in the present study. Vinogradov et al. (2008) studied the SSLC's amplitudes and phases globally including the open oceans using satellite data; they focused on the climatological means of a 13-year period. Their estimates differ slightly from ours; for example, most amplitude values they found were <10 cm, (in a few cases reaching 15 cm), whereas we find that 95% of the tide gauges have mean amplitudes up to 18 cm or more (with several locations over 20 cm). This indicates that altimetry data may underestimate the SSLC amplitudes along the coast, especially because their study does not consider barometric pressure effects and the inverted barometer. Our data still retain air pressure effects, which may explain some of the differences, particularly at higher latitudes (Ponte, 2006). However, the general spatial patterns are consistent in that we observe relatively higher amplitude values in the Western Pacific, specifically in regions like East Asia and Northern Australia.

Wahl et al. (2014) used the same approach as we do here to assess non-stationarity for the U.S. Gulf Coast where they compared the amplitude changes pre- and post-1990s. In our study we highlight the time periods of the first decade containing data post-1970 and the last decade of each respective tide gauge record. For the South China Sea, Amiruddin et al. (2015) explored the temporal variability in the SSLC and found some high variability in the annual amplitudes, which coincides with our results showing that some locations in this region can reach standard deviations of up to 2.8 cm from their annual amplitude. Annual amplitudes have varied over time at most of our study locations. At over 70% of all the tide gauges analyzed, the maximum amplitudes occurred after 1970, with a tendency to peak during the most recent decade in North America. Small ratios of mean to maximum ASLC values reveal locations where amplitude changes are more apparent. For example, the smallest ratios are found in Warnemunde and Wismar in Germany. Other examples of tide gauges with small ratios include Alexandroupolis within the Mediterranean Sea, Pago Pago, Midway Island and La Libertad II in the Pacific, and Dikson in Russia where we suspect influences by changes in seasonal ice cover (Ruiz- Etcheverry et al., 2015).

Our estimates of circular mean annual phase indicate that for most of the tide gauges in our global analysis, the ASLC peaks during the fall season, which overlaps with the most active storm seasons in the Pacific and Atlantic basins (Oey & Chou, 2016; Roustan et al., 2022). To identify where the phase deviates from its mean over time, we map the circular standard deviation of the phase (Figure 5b). We notice several regions that exhibit a high circular standard deviation such as the Mediterranean, Baltic, some Pacific Islands, and the northeastern coast of North America. The latter region includes several tide gauges located in river mouths or (complex) bay systems where river runoff can influence the seasonal cycle (Pugh & Woodworth, 2014). For instance, the tide gauge at Bar Harbor in Frenchman Bay, Maine (circular standard deviation of 31°) exhibits a phase shift from May to October in the beginning of the record but is more concentrated from June to August past the 1980s and has remained between July and August after the late 1990s. This region of high deviation is one of comparatively low mean amplitude values (around 6 cm or less).

Another extreme example with a very dispersed phase (circular standard deviation of 33°) is Swinoujscie, Poland, where peaks have occurred during every month of the year at some point in the record; although most of those peaks are observed during July, August, and September. In general, we find that locations with a higher circular standard deviation of the phase have a less pronounced seasonal cycle (Dunne et al., 2012) and contain more interannual variability in the ASLC amplitude. Locations with a more discernible seasonal pattern (e.g., Japan, Key West, etc.) have less deviation in their phase. For example, locations where the ASLC is not very pronounced are found in the Mediterranean, specifically in Greece, and also in the Pacific Island of Pago Pago, and South Africa. Locations of high standard deviation (where the phase spreads out around a month or more) are scattered around the globe but most commonly found in (semi-)enclosed basins, Pacific Islands, and near bays. Large circular standard deviation values are also found in Russia, which is a distinct region due to its proximity to the North Pole. The seasonal sea level variability in the Russian Arctic seas is influenced by several additional processes such as ice cover and increased storm activity, etc. (Medvedev, 2021).

From our cluster analysis (Figure 7), tide gauge stations along the southeast U.S. coast (Cluster 3) and those north of Cape Hatteras (Cluster 2) show increasing ASLC amplitudes after the 1990s, with trends of 0.5 mm/year or more. For example, in Key West, the amplitude values did not surpass 10 cm until 1993. For the southeast U.S. similar results were reported in Calafat et al. (2018). More than 75% of the 226 tide gauges with significant trends post-1970 show amplitude changes at a rate of ± 0.5 mm/year or more. In contrast with the US clusters, Figure 4a shows strong negative trends for locations in the Baltic Sea where the annual amplitude is decreasing more than 2 mm/year in some parts. Hünicke and Zorita (2008) find increasing trends in the amplitude in their study of the Baltic Sea, but they analyzed the entire 20th century whereas our trend analysis takes data from the 1970s

onwards, including more recent data than was available at the time of their study. While annual amplitudes in the Baltic have followed an increasing centennial trend, it turned negative for the last several decades. Our cluster analysis in this region (Figure 8b) shows a recovery of the amplitude in the recent decade, in agreement with the small differences in exceedances (Figure 4b) despite a strong negative trend. Although the amplitude was found to have changed over time, the phase has remained relatively stable in the Baltic. That is, as reported by Hünicke and Zorita (2008), the ASLC reaches a minimum in spring months and high peaks in winter which aligns with our findings. These tide gauges in the Baltic show a coherent spatial pattern of significant amplitude differences during the strongest years of the AMO and the NAO.

When clustering the northwestern Atlantic region post-1990, we find strong regional coherence among Cluster 1 and Cluster 3, located to the north and south of Cape Hatteras, respectively. Their cluster means explain over 95% of the variances in the annual amplitude time series of the tide gauges clustered. While both show increasing amplitudes, the variability is different, as also reported by Calafat et al. (2018). Cape Hatteras is the point where the Gulf Stream detaches from the coast, and Woodworth et al. (2019), for example, suggest wind-forcing and the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) to play a role in the distinction of MSL variability in the regions north and south of Cape Hatteras on decadal timescales. Overall, we find clear spatial patterns where large-scale climate modes lead to coherent increases or decreases of the ASLC amplitudes. Those are consistent with known influences of the same modes on sea level and wave variability in general, for example, El Niño leading to higher MSL and extreme wave events along the U.S. West coast and positive NAO leading to higher sea level and storm waves over the North Sea, Baltic Sea, and Mediterranean (Barnard et al., 2015; Han et al., 2019; Patra et al., 2020). This composite analysis only provides a first step toward understanding processes driving changes in ASLC amplitudes and more in-depth assessments are needed leveraging additional observations of meteorological (e.g., pressure, wind) and oceanographic (e.g., steric sea level) variables and/or ocean models.

6. Conclusions

We performed a global coastal ASLC analysis. Using a harmonic regression and clustering methods, we assessed mean values for the ASLC components and quantified changes over time, identifying hotspots where either amplitude or phase changes were most pronounced. Globally, we find higher mean annual amplitudes along the coasts of the Pacific and Indian Ocean. In such places, the ASLC plays a significant role in local seasonal sea level variability. Changes in the ASLC amplitude feature spatial variability across the globe, but when focusing on the North Atlantic we find coherent variations in individual regions especially on the east coast of the U.S. Changes in the annual amplitude over time were significant in 226 locations, with both negative and positive trends.

In addition to the annual amplitudes, we also assessed the variability in the annual phases and found that the peaks in sea level tend to occur during the fall season of the year for the respective hemispheres, but some tide gauge locations exhibit strong variability or long-term changes in the phase over time. For example, tide gauge sites in the Pacific Islands and in the Mediterranean have phases dispersed throughout many months of the year. Both changes reported here in terms of annual amplitude and phase can lead to higher base water levels on which storm surges or extreme waves can be superimposed, thereby leading to increased flooding risk. Finally, we also link changes in the ASLC amplitudes to climate indices which exert coherent influences on the ASLC amplitudes for long connected coastline stretches. ASLC variations in the deep ocean differ from those in shallow water (Pugh & Woodworth, 2014) analyzed here. Therefore, it is of interest to extend our analysis of the ASLC beyond coastal tide gauges by incorporating satellite altimetry and ocean model data to fully capture the global behavior of the ASLC. Based on the results presented and discussed here, future research steps could include (a) using complementary observational data and model experiments to identify the underlying mechanisms of ASLC variation; (b) incorporating offshore locations in understanding ASLC patterns and their seasonal changes globally; (c) linking the MSL seasonality patterns to the other extreme sea level oceanographic components such as ocean wave and storm surge events (Reinert et al., 2021); and (d) linking ASLC and extreme sea level variability to atmospheric patterns and drivers at multiple timescales.

Data Availability Statement

The monthly MSL data used for harmonic analysis are available at PSMSL's website: <https://psmsl.org/data/obtaining/>. The climate indices used for comparison with the sea level annual amplitudes are available at NOAA's

Physical Sciences Laboratory: <https://psl.noaa.gov/data/climateindices/list/#Nina34>. The codes used to run the model and additional analyses are uploaded on the following GitHub repository: <https://github.com/CoRE-Lab-UCF/AnnualSeaLevel>.

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